

Environmental Education Concern in India

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Since the evolution of man on the earth he had been dependent on the environment. Initially his number was small and needs limited. Therefore, his activities did not affect the environment. Much slowly, he settled down, became civilized and learnt how to cultivate. As time passed, the development of science and technology made the life more and more comfortable, and man also became more and more ambitious. With such development, human dependence on environment increased; he consumed more resources and the effect of his activities on the environment became more and more visible. With the industrial revolution the consumption of raw materials such as wood, minerals, coal and fossil fuels increased tremendously and with time the pollution of air, water and soil become visible. This made the man more conscious of his actions and the consequences. Slowly, it was realized that the existence of human race itself was in danger and to survive as a race it was necessary to educate about the environment, its repercussion could be minimized. This led to the development of concept of Environmental Education (EE).

Environmental education is a process of providing learning experiences to obtain knowledge understanding, skills and awareness with desirable attitudinal changes about man's relationship with his natural and man made surroundings which includes the relation of population, pollution, resource allocation, transportation, technology and urban and rural planning to the total human environment. Environmental education must utilize diverse learning environment and a broad array of educational approaches to teaching learning about and from the environment with due stress on practical activities and first hand experiences. It should help learners to discover the symptoms and real causes of environmental problems and thus to develop critical thinking and problem solving skills. Environmental education should be a continuous life long process, beginning at the pre school stage level and continuing through all formal and non formal stages and should

be interdisciplinary discipline or making possible a holistic and balanced perspective.

The Stockholm conference in 1972 at Stockholm adopted "Declaration on the human environment" and "Declaration of principles". In short, the declaration states that the man is both creature and moulder of his environment and the protection and improvement of human environment is a major issue for the survival of human race. His capability to transform his surroundings is used wisely can bring to all peoples the benefits of development and if wrongly applied can do incalculable harm to human beings. In developing countries most of the environmental problems are caused by under development and the development in these countries must be directed bearing in mind the need to safeguard and improve the environment. The natural growth of population continuously presents problems for the preservation of the environment. The Stockholm conference approved an action plan with a focus on human settlement management, natural resource management; pollution; educational informational, social and cultural aspects and the development and its effects on the environment and measures to get rid of problems of poverty while avoiding or minimizing the destruction and pollution of the environment the environment scenario of India is very wide indeed. At the first level, special attention must be paid to the school going children and women. They are to be made aware of health, nutrition, sanitation, hygiene, development water, and food contamination, fodder and fuel wood etc. non government organizations NGO's have to play a significant role, in the directory of department of environment, there are 200 NGO's which work in the area of environmental education and awareness. The chief goals of Environmental Education in India must be :

- To improve the quality of environment.
- To create an environment among people on environmental protection.

environments both natural and man made and its role in contemporary society.

- A fundamental understanding of bio-physical environmental problems confronting man, how these problems can be solved and the responsibilities of the citizens and government to work towards their solution.
- Attitude of concern for the quality of bio-physical environment that will motivate citizens to participate in bio-physical environment problem solving.

Status of Environmental Education in India

The importance of environment has been recognized in India since long. This is also reflected in its constitution, wherein it states :

It shall be the duty of every citizen to protect and improve the natural environment, including forests, lakes, rivers and wildlife and to have compassion for living creatures.

Article 51 A(g)

The importance of EE is reflected in National Policy on Education (NPE 1986 and 1992) in the following words:

8.15 there is paramount need to create a consciousness of the environment. It must permeate

all ages and all sections of the society; beginning with the child environmental consciousness should inform teaching in school and colleges. This aspect be integrated in entire educational process.

Formal Education

Environmental Education has percolated to all aspects of education including primary, secondary and tertiary education through formal and informal system of education. This has been schematically shown in figure.

Environmental Education has the target population that includes students, teachers, doctors, engineers, and common man. For this reason one has to use both formal and informal system of education. The objective of Environmental Education include opportunities to acquire the knowledge, values, skills, attitudes, commitment and improve the environment and to create new patterns of behaviour of individual group and society as a whole towards society. It therefore, requires that appropriate action takes place in the behaviour to protect and improve the environment. Since the basic objectives of Environmental Education is not environment itself but concern environmental problems the successful Environmental Education programme includes development of correct values and attitudes towards environment.

Environmental Education

- To develop the capabilities of decision making.

The Concept of Environmental Education

The area of Environmental Education has been discussed thoroughly at several national and international seminars, workshops and conferences. Most of the people have recognized the urgent need of environmental education, but only some have clear idea and understanding about the concept of Environmental Education that need to be taught to the students of education. Environmental education has been defined in different manner by various persons. The definition of environmental education in the draft of US environmental education Act is considered to be very authentic and is frequently quoted. It states :

“Environmental Education is an integral process which deals with man’s interrelationship with his natural and man made surrounding, including the rate of population growth, pollution resource allocation and depletion, conservation technology and urban and rural planning to the total human environment. Environmental education is a study of the factors influencing eco systems, mental and physical health, living and working conditions, decaying cities and population pressures. Environmental Education is intended to promote among citizens the awareness and understanding of environment our relation to it and the concern and responsible action necessary to assure our survival and to improve the quality of life”.

The Tbilisi conference recommended the following guiding principles for Environmental Education :

Environmental Education should

- Consider the environment in its totality natural and built, technological and social.
- Be a continuous life long processes, beginning at the pre-school level and continuing through all formal and non formal states.
- Enable learners to have a role in planning their learning experiences and provide an opportunity for making decisions and accepting their consequences.
- Be interdisciplinary in its approach, drawing on the specific content of each discipline in making possible holistic and balanced perspective. In interdisciplinary model relevant components of many disciplines are drawn to create an unit of Environmental Education as shown in figure :
- be centered on practical problems related to real life.
- Aim at building up sense of values.

Based on these characteristics the programme for Environmental Education are designed at different levels. The objectives of Environmental Education are drawn on the basis of objectives, described in Belgrade Carter. In practical terms the objectives of Environmental Education have been stated by stapp et. al. as follows :

- A clear understanding that man is inseparable part of a system, consisting of man, cultural and biophysical environment and the man has ability to alter the interrelation of this region.
- A broad understanding of bio physical

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School Education

In this method of incorporation of Environmental Education in the school curricula, the environment concerns are included in already existing curriculum. National curriculum for elementary and secondary education states two general objectives related to Environmental Education along with other objectives these are

- i. Understanding of environment and its limited resources and the need for conservation of natural resources and energy
- ii. Appreciation of various consequences of large families and over population & need of checking population growth.

In 1985, Ministry of HRD launched the scheme of Environment orientation of school education. This scheme is implemented in states and union territories through education department and voluntary agencies having expertise and interest in Environmental Education.

At senior secondary level, there is also a vocational course in India. It contains general foundation course which is allotted 15% of time. Out of this 15% has been given to EE and Rural Development.

University Education

There are about 15 universities for teaching environmental sciences. University education has three major components: Teaching, Research and Extension. At post graduate level four major areas are recognized.

Environment Engineering

It includes subject like architecture, civil engineering, town and country planning including water engineering, slum improvement.

Conservation and Management

Includes fields like land use, forestry, agriculture, energy & waste management etc.

Environment Health

Deals with public health and Hygiene, sanitary

and chemical engineering nutrition and drug, etc.

Social Ecology

It includes subjects like ecology, sociology, social planning, psych. Counselling etc.

There are several government and non governmental organizations to educate people and to create awareness of environment. A Department of environment has been set up in 1982 as environment information system for this purpose. There is a centre for Environmental Education (CEE) at Ahmedabad. There are more than 200 private organization working for environmental Education.

Conclusion

A large variety of approaches have been used for EE. These include legislative efforts, curriculum based approach that goes with formal education system & informal approaches through camps, seminars, films, media. In formal system also there is variety. The co curricular activities of education are the most appropriate means for action, the teacher is the main means for implementing the programmes and realizing the objectives of EE and organization of co curricular activities in school and outside the school. There are two main programmes recommended by educational commission and policy i.e. NSS and NLPW. Many organization and institutions both govt. and private play the role of env. Educators. NCERT, CEE, Forest departments, MHRD plays a leading role in this. Seminars, conferences and seminars are organized for this purpose. An such conference was held in India was international conference on Environmental Education, 1981 it touches upon almost every aspect of Environmental Education.

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